

Real-time simulation of surgical cutting in haptic environments using computational vademecums

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The realistic simulation of surgical cutting is difficult in real-time, since it modifies the geometry and topology of the mesh, and it has to be done with no penalization of the computation time. Here we present the preliminary results of a novel technique to achieve it by PGD. Computational vademecums are used jointly with XFEM-based techniques, and the computing workload is distributed into an off-line and an on-line stage. During the off-line stage, both a computational vademecum for any position of a load and the displacements produced by a set of cuts are pre-computed for the organ under consideration. Thus, during the on-line stage, the pre-computed results are properly combined together to obtain, in real-time, the response to the actions driven by the user. By way of example, the cutting method is applied to the simulation of a corneal refractive surgical procedure known as radial keratotomy.